

An Investigation Into the Effect of Liquid Viscosity on the Performance of an Oil Well

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ABSTRACT

Liquid viscosity is an important fluid property that can affect the productivity of an oil and gas well. Therefore, petroleum engineers must investigate this parameter to determine the most efficient way to mitigate the impact, while improving the performance of an oil and gas well to save resources and overall cost for future projects. To investigate the research question on “How liquid viscosity affects well performance”, we elected to use PIPESIM to perform a sensitivity analysis on how API gravity affects oil production rate and well flowing pressure, since there is a strong correlation between API gravity and viscosity of a fluid. Beggs and Robinsons correlation forms the foundation of the method chosen. For a vertical well with a static pressure of 4000psi, a temperature of 175°F, API gravity of 32°API and a productivity index of 2.5STB/d/psi were some of the parameters adopted during this investigation. From the simulation, it was observed that the higher the API value, the higher the flowrate. Whereas the opposite effect was observed for the well flowing pressure as this significantly reduced, confirming an indirect relationship between the API gravity and viscosity. In addition, it was observed that the maximum operating conditions occurred between 40° and 46° API, as two values produced the same flowrate of 3163.95 STB/day offering the suggestion that after a certain degree of API gravity (viscosity) there would be no pronounced effect on further flowrate. To conclude, the findings will imply that viscosity has a negative impact on productivity, however, can be mitigated with methods such as gas injection, steam flooding and in-situ combustion, in order to increase the API gravity.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Definition
API	American Petroleum Institute
IPR	Inflow Performance Relationship
EOR	Enhanced Oil Recovery
OPR	Outflow Performance Relationship

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CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

➤ *Viscosity:*

Viscosity is the resistance to the flow of a fluid, with research suggesting that fluids with low viscosity flow easier than those with higher ones (Wang et al, 1964). This parameter is greatly important, as it can seriously hinder the production of an oil well. Therefore, a lack of research into viscosity could prove costly, especially with the global issue of climate change brought on by fossil fuels adding increased pressure to the oil and gas industry. Oil wells must be capable of producing hydrocarbons in short time to satisfy the demand.

➤ *Focus of the Research:*

As fossil fuels are non-renewable, there is a growing need to enhance the production of hydrocarbon and oil-well performance. However, to achieve this desired result there needs to be a detailed study of reservoir rock and fluid properties such as porosity, permeability, viscosity, and oil formation volume factor. These variables all form a crucial part of the production of hydrocarbons and require investigation to reduce their limitations to productivity. Therefore, this research will aim to investigate the variable ‘viscosity’ and how viscosity affects the productivity of an oil well.

➤ *PIPESIM:*

In recent years, the ability to investigate reservoir rock and fluid properties has significantly increased. Software such as ‘PIPESIM’ has revolutionised how petroleum engineers can investigate the effects caused by these properties, allowing the creation of simulations to optimise the productivity of the well and thus saving time and money in the efforts of acquiring hydrocarbons. PIPESIM is software, that allows a researcher to model an oil well and analyse the impact of different variables through sensitivity analysis.

➤ *Aims of the Research:*

The group aimed to investigate the following question:

- “How does liquid viscosity affect the oil well performance and optimised operating conditions?”

The research will use quantitative methods, applying Beggs and Robinsons’ correlation to determine API gravity as well as, the use of computer-aided simulation with PIPESIM to perform a sensitivity analysis to determine the optimal operating conditions for the well.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

➤ *How Does Viscosity Affect the IPR Productivity:*

In recent times, investigations into oil well performance formed the concept of the ‘Inflow Performance Curve’, which demonstrated the relationship between the flowing bottom pressure ‘P’ and oil production rate ‘Q’ (Gilbert, 1954). This research is critical to understand how varying factors can affect the performance of a well and allow the mitigation of negatives reducing productivity.

In petroleum engineering, the inflow performance relationship is viewed as one of the most fundamental diagnostic tools to evaluate the performance of a flowing well (Basaleh, 2020). An accurate IPR is used to provide the optimum production scheme and maximise reservoir production efficiency. However, several mitigating variables can impact this measurement such as viscosity, skin factor, reservoir temperature, and non-darcy coefficient (Basaleh, 2020). The variable ‘viscosity’ is of significant interest of its nature to reduce the flow speed within the reservoir, resulting in a lower overall productivity index. Support for this idea comes from Guo, who claims that the combination of permeability and viscosity affects the results within the lower oil rate at given bottom-hole pressure (Guo, 2017). Likewise, it further claims that the IPR curve will suffer a deviation from the linear trendline present in Fig.1. (Guo, 2017).

Fig 1 Typical IPR Curve. (Guo, 2017)

➤ *How Does Viscosity Affect the Well Performance:*

Understanding the effect viscosity has on oil well performance is crucial for any petroleum engineer trying to maximise the operating point / operating conditions during the production of hydrocarbons. Proposed by Wang, viscosity relates to the resistance a fluid feels when it tries to flow, suggesting that fluids with lower viscosity’s flow easier than those with a high viscosity (Wang et al., 1964). Their research implies that it is essential to reduce the viscosity, to provide the fastest flow of fluid. Supporting this research is Gokcal, who performed an investigation into the effect of viscosity on both low and high-viscosity flow loops, concluding higher discrepancies for the high-viscosity oils in comparison to the low-viscosity ones (Gokcal et al., 2008). In their claims, they base these findings on the higher ones being more carefully examined however, the fact there is a higher degree of uncertainty with the higher viscosity supports Wang’s claim of higher viscosities being more resistant to flow, moreover emphasising the negative associated with the liquid viscosity and flow pattern. In contrast, their study was conducted within a lab-based environment, subjecting the study to a lack of ecological validity and discounting the possibility of extraneous variables that may affect the flow within a real-life scenario, making it difficult to generalise the findings.

➤ *Temperature Effect on Viscosity:*

Beggs and Robinson developed a relationship between temperature and viscosity (see Appendix A). Their findings show that between 100°F to 150°F the effect of temperature greatly impacts flow rate, based on the previous relationship it suggests a decrease in viscosity. However, the capability of their method appears limited to only above 150°F. Moreover, Lee and Lee confirmed their theory as they also discovered a significant relationship between temperature and viscosity. They suggested that a decrease in viscosity occurs from an increase in temperature and that the more viscous a fluid is, the more sensitive it is to temperature change (Lee and Lee, 2019). This researcher also places emphasis on how improved viscosity contrast favours oil flow better than water flow (Lee and Lee, 2019). The literature suggests that to reduce the viscosity, the temperature must increase. This claim is backed up by Seeton, who suggests most liquids experience an exponential relationship (Seeton, 2006). This is emphasised by certain enhanced oil recovery (EOR) methods, such as in-situ combustion and steam injection as they rely on inducing high temperatures to alter the crude oil viscosity.

➤ *The Effect of API on Viscosity:*

The economic value of crude oil and field development decisions are significantly influenced by the API gravity. Since it aids in the design of the equipment used for exploration and field productivity in addition to the oil value, it has a significant impact on the economic viability of producing fields (Santos et al., 2018). Beal correlated the viscosity of dead oil as a function of API (Beal, 1946) (Beggs and Robinson, 1975). By claiming it is a function, the researcher highlights a direct relationship between the two. Although, Ubong disputes this claiming their correlations are of limited accuracy because of the variation between geological, lithological, and petrophysical conditions (Ubong,2014). (Bergman and Sutton, 2007) proposed the use of Watson characterization factor to account for this anomaly, especially with crude oils with less than 25°API. In addition to this, some EOR methods such as those aforementioned and miscible gas injection can be used to alter the API gravity of crude oils, ultimately influencing oil viscosity.

$$\begin{aligned}
 X &= Y(T - 460)^{-1.163} \\
 Y &= 10^Z \\
 Z &= 3.0324 - 0.02023^\circ API
 \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging all these and making API gravity the subject of the formula will give

$$^\circ API = \frac{3.0324 - Z}{0.02023} \quad (3)$$

Hence;

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z &= \frac{\log Y}{\log 10} \\
 Y &= \frac{X}{(T - 460)^{-1.163}} \quad \text{or} \quad Y = X(T - 460)^{1.163} \\
 X &= \frac{\log(\mu_{od} + 1)}{\log 10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Subsequently, we used MS Excel to calculate API gravities at different viscosities and at a constant temperature (175°F). Refer to Table 5 in the appendix section.

CHAPTER FOUR RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

➤ *Results and Discussions for Liquid Flowrate:*

As discussed in the methodology section of this report, the simulation produced a liquid flow rate of 2730.457 stb/day at an inlet pressure of 4000 psi and an assumed outlet pressure of 400 psi.

Fig 3 P/T Profile

➤ *Results and Discussions for Nodal Analysis:*

Nodal analysis was carried out to obtain the operating point at a viscosity of 3.5cp (calculated by PIPESIM) and a corresponding API gravity of 32°API which yielded a liquid flowrate of 2730.46 stb/day and a well flowing pressure of 2878.81 psi at the node (below the tubing).

Fig 4 Nodal Analysis (IPR and OPR)

➤ *Results and Discussions for Sensitivity Analysis:*

A sensitivity analysis was carried out to investigate the effect of oil viscosity (API gravity) on well performance and optimal operating point below and above base viscosity (API gravity) value. From our results, we observed that at a viscosity of 20cp (14.95°API), there was no operating point. However, as the viscosity decreased to 1.5cp and 1.0cp (API gravity increased to 40.73°API and 46.72°API), there was a significant increase in flowrate of 3163.95 stb/day and a decrease in well flowing pressure of 2734.16 psi.

Fig 5 Sensitivity Analysis (IPRs and OPRs)

CONCLUSION

Based on our findings, it can be said that the well productivity increases with decreasing liquid viscosity (higher API gravity) and decreases with increasing liquid viscosity (lower API gravity). Our investigation showed that the maximum operating conditions occurred at 1.5cp (40.73°API) and 1.0cp (46.72°API), however, the optimal operating point would be at a viscosity of 1.5cp because there was no shift in the operating point to the right of the IPR/OPR curve at a further reduction in viscosity. Because various assumptions were made in order to simplify the model that was employed, it should be noted that this conclusion has certain limits. Furthermore, the viscosity function needs to be added to the software to make it simpler to perform a sensitivity analysis on well performance with PIPESIM.

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APPENDIX

Fig 6 Beggs and Robinsons Correlation

Table 1 PVT Data for Simulation

Reservoir Fluid	Oil/Water/Gas
Water Cut	0
Solution GOR	650 (SCF/STB)
Oil Gravity	32(API)
Gas Gravity	0.65
Water Salinity	75000 (ppm)

Table 2 Deviation Survey

Measured Depth (feet)	True Vertical Depth (feet)
0	0
1000	1000
1500	1500
1954	1950
2262	2250
3077	3000
8993	8000
12672	11000
12960	11200
13435	11500

Table 3 Geothermal Data

Measured depth (feet)	Temperature (°F)
0	60
13400	175

Table 4 Tubing Configuration

Label	Equipment Type	MD (feet)	ID (inches)	Roughness (inches)
Wellhead	Xmas Tree	0	N.A	N/A
Tubing	Tubing	1100	3.992	0.0006
Safety Valve	SSSV	1100	3.6	N/A
Tubing	Tubing	13000	3.992	0.0006
Casing	Casing	13400	6.13	0.0006

	Equipment	Name	Active	MD
				ft
1		NA	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13200
2	SSSV	SSSV 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1100

Fig 7 Downhole Equipment

CASING/LINER							
Section type	Name	From MD	To MD	ID	Wall thickness	Roughness	
		ft	ft	in	in	in	
1	Casing	CsgSn 1	0	13400	6.13	0.361	0.0006

TUBINGS					
Name	To MD	ID	Wall thickness	Roughness	
	ft	in	in	in	
1	Tubing	13000	3.992	0.3065	0.006

Fig 8 Casing and Tubing

REFERENCE OPTIONS			
Depth reference:	Original RKB		
Wellhead depth:	0	ft	
Bottom depth:	13400	ft	

	MD	TVD	Horizontal dis...	Angle
	ft	ft	ft	deg
1	0	0	0	0
2	1000	1000	0	0
3	1500	1500	0	7.611304
4	1954	1950	60.13319	13.08735
5	2262	2250	129.8756	23.03802
6	3077	3000	448.8191	32.31031
7	8993	8000	3610.948	35.36921
8	12672	11000	5740.511	46.01704
9	12960	11200	5947.74	49.82223
10	13425	11500	6303.022	0

Fig 9 Deviation Survey Data

	MD	Ambient temp...	U Value
	ft	degF	Btu/(h.deg...
1	0	60	5
2	13400	175	5

Fig 10 Geothermal Data

STOCK TANK PROPERTIES			CONTAMINANT MOLE FRACTIONS	
Watercut	0	%	CO2 fraction:	0
GOR	650	SCF/STB	H2S fraction:	0
Gas specific gravity:	0.64		N2 fraction:	0
Water specific gravity:	1.02		H2 fraction:	0
API	30	dAPI	CO fraction:	0

Fig 11 PVT Data 1

UNDERSATURATED OIL	MIXTURE
Correlation: Vasquez & Beggs	Emulsion viscosity method: Set to viscosity of the continuous p...
LIVE OIL VISCOSITY	Inversion watercut: <input checked="" type="radio"/> Specify <input type="radio"/> Calculate
Correlation: Beggs & Robinson	60 %
DEAD OIL	
Correlation: Beggs & Robinson	
Temperature (1st): 175 degF	
Viscosity (1st): 3.528077 cP	
Temperature (2nd): 60.00001 degF	
Viscosity (2nd): 79.15489 cP	

Fig 12 PVT Data 2

Table 5 Viscosity and API Gravity Data from MS Excel

$\mu_{od}(cp)$	X @T=175°F	Y	Z	API (°)
1	0.301029996	122.2539846	2.087263023	46.71957375
1.5	0.397940009	161.610977	2.208470856	40.72808425
2.5	0.544068044	220.9563408	2.344306469	34.01352105
5	0.77815125	316.0219658	2.49971727	26.33132624
20	1.322219295	536.9783066	2.729956741	14.95023524

Table 6 Sensitivity Analysis Result

$\mu_{od}(cp)$	API (°)	Q (stb/day)	Pwf (psi)
1.0	46.72	3163.95	2734.42
1.5	40.73	3163.95	2734.42
2.5	34.01	2876.03	2828.85
3.5	32	2730.46	2878.81
5.0	26.33	3044.11	2260.74
20.0	14.95	-	-